

was concentrated to a gummy residue (6.5 g). Chromatography^{3,4} of a part of the residue (0.5 g) through Amberlite IR 120(H) and elution of the column for neutral and basic amino acids with distilled water and aqueous 4*N* HCl as described earlier⁵, led to the identification of proline, threonine and glycine by co-pc with authentic samples.

Another part of the residue (1.0 g) was chromatographed through Amberlite IRA 400(OH) and elution of the column with water and 2*N* acetic acid for neutral and acidic amino acids, led to the identification⁶ of proline, tyrosine, lysine, alanine, leucine, tryptophan, valine, threonine, aspartic acid and glutamic acid by co-pc with authentic samples. Proline and threonine were also found from the cation resin column.

All these amino acids were isolated from the mixture as their ninhydrin complexes by preparative pc⁶ on Whatmann paper (3 mm) using the solvent system *n*-BuOH–AcOH–H₂O (12 : 3 : 5) as the developing solvent and their relative occurrence (in $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) of the air-dried aerial parts estimated colorimetrically was found to be proline, 19.3; lysine, 2.5; tryptophan, 1.8; threonine, 1.2; glycine, 0.9; alanine, 0.9; tyrosine, 0.5; leucine, 0.4; valine, 0.3; glutamic acid, 0.2 and aspartic acid, 0.1. This appears to be the first report on amino acid composition of the genus, *Fleurya*.

Acknowledgement

The authors thanks Dr. N. K. Chakraborty, M. B. B. College, Agartala, for identification of plant species. Two of the authors (G.C. and A.D.) are thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Fluoride in Water

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Manuscript received 15 June 1987, revised 21 December 1987,
accepted 30 December 1987

FLUORIDES occur in the industrial effluents¹ and also in water flowing over fluoride-containing rocks and minerals. The TLV (threshold limit

value) as recommended by the American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists is 3 ppm in drinking water². The toxic effects of excess fluorides are well established^{2,3}.

The common methods of fluoride analysis are based on the bleaching action of fluorides on the coloured lake formed by various ligands with metal ions, viz. SPADNS and zirconyl chloride⁴, eriochrome cyanine R and zirconium, alizarin and cerium⁵ etc. The displaced dye differs sufficiently in colour from its metal chelate to permit determination of the fluoride ion concentration as a function of the colour change of the solution. Other spectrophotometric methods make use of liberation of the chelating dye with the addition of fluoride^{6,7}. Other methods include titrimetric⁸, fluorimetric⁹, potentiometric¹⁰ and ion-selective electrodes¹¹. All the available methods require close control of pH.

The present method is based on the bleaching action of fluoride on the purple coloured thorium-chromotrope 2B dye complex (λ_{max} 550 nm) and measurement of the decrease in colour intensity at 570 nm, i.e. the wavelength of maximum difference⁶; the pure dye has λ_{max} at 510 nm. The method is simple, rapid and sensitive.

Experimental

All spectral studies were made on a ECIL GS-865 and a Carl Zeiss Specol spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched glass cells.

Standard solution of fluoride (1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving sodium fluoride (A.R.; 0.211 g) in glass-distilled water (100 ml). A 0.002 *M* chromotrope 2B (*p*-nitrobenzeneazochromotropic acid) dye solution was prepared in glass-distilled water. A 0.001 *M* thorium nitrate solution was prepared in glass-distilled water.

Mixed reagent was always prepared fresh by mixing equal volumes of 0.002 *M* chromotrope 2B and 0.001 *M* thorium nitrate to give red-violet complex. Reference solution was prepared by combining the mixed reagent (1 ml) and 0.02 *M* HCl (0.2 ml) and the volume was made upto 10 ml with glass-distilled water. Solutions of diverse ions were made by the reported method¹².

Procedure : To the mixed reagent (1 ml) placed in a 10 ml volumetric flask, was added an aliquot of sample solution containing 2.5–20 μg of fluoride and the pH maintained at 2.5–3.0 by adding 0.02 *M* HCl. Then its volume was made upto the mark with glass-distilled water. After 1 min absorbance was measured at 570 nm against the reference solution.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of chromotrope 2B show that the dye has a maximum absorption at 510 nm. The dye-metal complex has maximum absorption at 550 nm. The maximum difference in the absorption

of test and reference solution was observed at 570 nm, which was used for spectrophotometric determinations (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra: (A) chromotrope 2B dye against water, and (B) chromotrope 2B dye + thorium against water.

The optimum pH for maximum color development was found in the range 2.5–3.0. At lower pH the dye was liberated even without the addition of fluoride and at higher pH the dye was not liberated at all. The reaction was rapid at room temperature. No change was observed upto 15–40°. The liberated dye was found to be stable for ~12 h. Absorbance values were maximum at molar ratio 1 : 1 of 0.002 M dye and 0.001 M thorium solutions.

Beer's law, determination limit and reproducibility: Beer's law is obeyed in the range 2.5–20 μg of fluoride per 10 ml. Reproducibility was checked by determining 10 μg of fluoride per 10 ml, over a period of 7 days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be 0.01 and 1.50%, respectively.

It was found that sodium, potassium, nitrate, nitrite and chloride do not interfere. Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Al^{III} which also form complexes with fluoride, interfere, which are removed by cation-exchange resins. Sulphates can be removed after precipitation as recommended¹⁸. However, most of the interferences are removed by distillation of fluoride prior to its determination as recommended¹¹.

Application of method: The method was applied for the determination of fluoride in drinking water and waste water. Waste water sample of fluoride contained a number of interfering anions and cations along with sulphate. It was therefore necessary to separate the fluoride by distillation¹¹ prior to analysis by the present method and SPADNS method. The results presented in Table 1 are in close agreement.

Conclusion: The present method is sensitive, rapid and easy to carry out. It can be successfully applied for the determination of fluoride in drinking and polluted river water.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF FLUORIDE IN POLLUTED RIVER WATER*

Sample no.	Fluoride found (Present method)	Fluoride found (SPADNS method)
	μg	μg
1.	9.2	9.0
2.	13.5	14.0
3.	22.0	22.5
4.	18.0	18.0
5.	5.3	5.0

*Sample of river water collected near the fertiliser factory was used after distillation.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head, Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, for facilities.

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An Improved Lindemann Method for Colorimetric Determination of Inorganic Phosphate in Biological Samples

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Manuscript received 21 April 1986, revised 3 September 1987, accepted 13 January 1988

THE Fiske–Subbarow method¹ for the quantitative determination of inorganic phosphate suffers from the lack of stability of the blue colour of the reduced phosphomolybdate complex. The method was modified by Lindemann² using a combination of hydrazine sulphate and stannous chloride, by Martland and Robison³ using quinols in sodium

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